

PREVENTION OF TRANSMISSION OF INFECTIOUS DISEASE: STUDIES ON HAND HYGIENE IN HEALTH-CARE AMONG STUDENTS

D.H.Tambekar, S.D. Shirsat, S.B.Suradkar, P.N. Rajankar and Y.S. Banginwar¹
Post Graduate Department of Microbiology, S.G.B. Amravati University, Amravati 444 602 (India)
Institute of Pharmacy, Kaulkhed, Akola¹ (India)

ABSTRACT

Hand washing is considered to be one of the primary mechanisms to reduce the risk of transmission of infectious agents by both the contact and fecal oral routes. The present study was on the effect of hand washing in preventing enteric infections among students of KG, primary, secondary and college. A total of 160 hand swab samples of 40 students were analysed before and after hand washing and maximum number of bacterial pathogens isolated included *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (37%) followed by *E.coli* (23%), *Proteus mirabilis* (20%), *Citrobacter freundii* (7%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (5%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (4%), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (3%) and *Salmonella typhi* (2%). There was complete removal of pathogens from the hands of 20% students after washing hands. The hands of remaining 80% students showed partial removal of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from left hand while complete removal of *Citrobacter freundii* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* from right hand after hand washings. *Salmonella typhi* was removed from both left and right hand after washing hands. The prevalence of the bacterial pathogens was high in students of KG and primary than collegiate. Hence, indicating that unwashed hand can transmit and hand washing can prevent the transmission of enteric pathogen to enter into the body among the students.

KEY WORDS: Hand washing, Infection, prevention, students

INTRODUCTION

Proper sanitation is important not only from the general health point of view but it has a vital role to play in our individual and social life too and hand hygiene is considered as the most important measure for preventing the spread of pathogens. It has long been recognized as an important procedure in preventing the transmission of disease (Larson, 1989). In developing countries, 80% of the diseases are associated with poor domestic and personal hygiene and about 2.2 million people; mostly children and school students die annually due to diarrhoea (WHO, 2006, Lankinen *et al*, 1994).

Entry of microorganism can be controlled by proper hand washing which reduce the rate of waterborne and food borne diseases (Antai, 2006). Drastic decrease in the bacterial count occurred due to surface sterilization in the process of hand washing with soap (Oniya *et al*, 2006). It was also reported that frequent hand washing represents an important element of hygiene that may interrupt transmission of organisms. Hand surface especially under the fingernails are reservoir of microorganisms (Rayan *et al*, 1987). Close environment, doorknobs and other inanimate objects serves as resting grounds for microbes and the contaminated hands serves as the vehicles of transmission. In schools and colleges students are more likely to take meal and water in recess without washing hands and they may pose to risk of infection.

The use of soap and hand washing promotion could achieve a 26-62% decrease in the incidence of diarrhoea in developing countries (Clemens and Stanton, 1987; Pinfold and Horan, 1996, Shahid *et al*, 1996). Hand washing remains the most effective and least expensive major to prevent transmission of infection. Most of the KG, primary, secondary school and collegiate students bring tiffin and take meal in the recess, without washing their hands, which may cause enteric infections. Therefore the present study was undertaken to identify bacterial pathogens associated with the hands and to find out percent reduction in infection rate related to poor hygiene after hand washing and to improve students overall health and well being by providing guidance on the importance of hand washing.

Fig. 1: Bacterial pathogens isolated from hand swab before and after hand washing

Bacterial Pathogens

Fig. 2: Bacterial pathogens isolated from hand swab before and after hand washing from students of different category.

Bacterial Pathogens

Fig. 3: Bacterial pathogens isolated from hand swab of different age groups of students

Bacterial Pathogens

Fig. 4: Bacterial pathogens isolated from hand swab of tiffin-holder and non-tiffin holder students

Bacterial Pathogens

Bacteria Pathogens	Before Hand Washing		After Hand Washing		Total Pathogen	Reduction after hand washing
	L.H.	R.H.	L.H.	R.H.		
<i>S. typhi</i>	02	01	0	0	3 (2%)	100%
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	12	17	12	16	57 (37%)	96%
<i>P.mirabilis</i>	07	13	05	06	31 (20%)	55%
<i>E. aerogenes</i>	01	02	01	0	4 (3%)	33%
<i>E.coli</i>	16	12	04	04	36 (23%)	28%
<i>C. freundii</i>	06	02	02	0	10 (6%)	25%
<i>S. aureus</i>	04	01	0	01	6 (4%)	20%
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	04	02	0	01	7 (5%)	17%
Total	52	50	24	20	154	43%

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 160 swab samples of 40 students were collected. Out of 40 students, 10 each from KG, primary, higher secondary and college students were randomly selected for study. The left hand and right hand of each student were swabbed before and after hand washing. Hands were washed thoroughly with water and soap.

Hands were swabbed with the help of sterilized cotton bud soaked in 0.85% saline solution and then these hand swabs were added directly into 5 mL MacConkey broth under aseptic conditions and incubated at 37°C for 24h. A 0.5ml broth culture from each was inoculated on sterilized MacConkey agar plate and uniformly spread and incubated at 37°C for 24h.

After incubation, numbers of CFU were counted and different types of colonies were isolated. The distinct colonies were screened and selected on the basis of morphology, cultural characteristics and identified on the basis of standard test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 160 hand swab samples were collected from total 40 students. Out of 40 students, 10 from KG, 10 from primary, 10 from secondary and 10 from collegiate students. From 160 swab samples, 132 samples were contaminated. Although there was a variety of bacterial species found on the hands of students. Bacteria isolated from hand swab include *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (37%) followed by *E.coli* (23%), *Proteus mirabilis* (20%), *Citrobacter freundii* (7%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (5%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (4%), *Enterobacter aerogenes* (3%) and *Salmonella typhi* (2%). The pathogens were generally higher in the samples on before hand washing than in the samples of after hand washing (Table 1).

The bacterial pathogens were generally higher in before hand washing samples. About 43% reduction was observed in after hand washing samples. There was complete removal of pathogen from the hands of 8 (20%) students after washing hands. The hands of remaining 32 (80%) students showed partial removal of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from left hand while complete removal of *Citrobacter freundii* and *Enterobacter aerogenes* from right hand after hand washing. *Salmonella typhi* (100%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (96%) were almost removed from both left and right hand after hand washing (Table 1). Oniya *et al* (2006) also reported *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. epidermidis* and *Bacillus subtilis* on the hands of the students. But the prevalence of these organisms was higher in before hand washing as compare to the after hand washing. Aiello *et al* (2004) also reported occurrence of *Enterobacter species* and *Staphylococcus species*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas species* on the hands. Prescott *et al*, (2005), Scott (1990) and Doring (1996) observed the incidence of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Lactobacillus* on human palms and reported transmissible by hand shaking.

Tambekar *et al* (2006) reported the presence of *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, *Citrobacter spp.*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* from hand swabs of students. The 24% hand swab sample showed decrease in microbial flora after hand washing. *Citrobacter freundii*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from the hands of the KG students (Fig. 1). These organisms along with *Enterobacter aerogenes* were isolated from the hands of primary students. *Salmonella typhi* was absent in secondary and collegiate student's palm. High percentage of bacterial contamination was found in KG and primary students as compare to the secondary and collegiate students. Oniya *et al* (2006) reported similarly. The prevalence of isolated organism including *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. epidermidis*, *Bacillus subtilis* were higher in primary and secondary school students as compare to the collegiate students (Fig. 2).

The swab samples were divided in 4 groups based on age of students. The prevalence of bacterial pathogens was higher in age group of students including 3 – 4 years and 5 – 9 years as compare to 10 – 13 years and 16-22 years students. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was higher on the hands of the students of 10-13 yrs and 16-22 yrs and *S. aureus* on 16-22 yr students. *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi* were not found on the hands of students of 10 -13 yr. *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were not found on the hands of the students of age group 3-4 yr. *Salmonella typhi* was absent on the hands of the students of 16-22 yr (Fig. 3). It was observed that there were higher bacterial pathogens isolated from tiffin holder students than non-tiffin holder students. The prevalent bacterial pathogens in tiffin users was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* followed by *E. coli*, *Proteus*

mirabilis, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Fig. 4).

CONCLUSION

Proper hand washing and safe food water handling can control the most of the waterborne and food borne diseases. There was drastic decrease in the bacterial count after washing hands than in before hand washing which reduces the risk of entry of pathogens in body. All the students were found to harbor the pathogenic bacteria on their hands before hand washing. The present study showed clear evidence of 50 % decrease in the microbial flora after hand washing. Therefore it was concluded that only a simple act of hand washing could prevent the enteric pathogens to enter in to the body and produce disease.

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Corresponding Author:

D.H.Tambekar

Post Graduate Department of Microbiology, S.G.B. Amravati University, Amravati 444 602 (India)